

homogenized in 1.16% KCl or 0.25 M Sucrose or 0.05 M Tris-HCl buffer pH 7.6. On the contrary, the goat submaxillary preparation catalysed the iodination of MIT very efficiently under identical conditions (Table 1). Fig 1. describes the formation

TABLE 1—IODINATION OF MIT BY GOAT OR SHEEP SUBMAXILIARY GLAND EXTRACT

System	I ⁻ incorporated (n moles/min/mg. protein)
Goat (0.20 mg)	21.13
Sheep (0.22 mg)	0.18
Sheep (0.44 mg)	0.22

700×g supernatant of both goat and sheep submaxillary extracts were used in this experiment.

of DIT from MIT when the goat enzyme preparation was used. In contrast, using the sheep preparation no DIT formation could be detected. It was naturally thought that this lack of activities in SSE might be due to the absence of these enzymes or if these enzymes are present they remain in an inactive form by the presence of an inhibitor. In order to check whether our extraction procedure was efficient, the sheep submaxillary gland was extracted with various buffers of various pH and the extracts were treated separately with protease, trypsin, chymotrypsin, trypsin plus chymotrypsin and mild heat treatment to get the enzyme released. None of these treatments however indicated the presence of iodinase or peroxidase activities in sheep submaxillary extracts (unpublished data).

To check whether SSE contains any inhibitor of iodinase or peroxidase, iodination reaction was carried out by adding SSE to goat enzyme preparation. Table 2 shows that SSE inhibited

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF SHEEP SUBMAXILIARY EXTRACT ON THE IODINATING ACTIVITY OF GOAT SUBMAXILIARY EXTRACT

System	I ⁻ incorporated (n moles/min/mg protein)
Goat (0.21 mg)	21.0
Goat (0.21 mg) + SSE (0.22 mg)	12.1
Goat (0.21 mg) + albumin (0.20 mg)	22.0

In this experiment 105,000×g supernatant of both SSE and goat enzyme preparation were used as bulk of the enzyme as well as the inhibitor are present in the soluble supernatant.

the iodination of MIT catalysed by goat enzyme. The possibility that the inhibitory action of SSE might be due to a competition between iodination of MIT and the protein of SSE as protein can be iodinated. This possibility is ruled out when addition of equal amounts of albumin failed to produce any inhibition of MIT iodination (Table 2).

Addition of increasing concentrations of SSE to the goat enzyme preparation produced a progressive inhibition of MIT iodination whereas it had little effect on peroxidase activity of goat enzyme. Non-dialysability, thermolability and loss of inhibitory

activity on protease treatment indicate that the inhibitor is protein in nature. None of the substrates of iodide peroxidase like MIT, KI and H₂O₂ competes with the inhibitor (Results of these experiments will be published elsewhere). However, the final proof depends on the isolation of the inhibitor in pure form. Attempts are in progress to isolate, purify and study the mode of action of this inhibitor. Although some antithyroid agents are known to inhibit the iodination reaction but no one has yet demonstrated the presence of a naturally occurring protein inhibitor which inhibits significantly the iodination reaction.

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Effect of Temperature on Non-Faradaic Electrolysis

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ONE of the authors has reported^{1,2} that electrolysis of water or dilute alkali metal sulphate solution (~N/1000) at low current density (at or below 5mA/cm²) with platinum electrodes show in general three anomalies, viz.

(1) Volume deficit, (2) Ratio Anomaly, (3) Co-liberation.

These anomalies have been lately confirmed by Gosnell and Venugopalan³ and discussed by others³. Such an electrolytic process has been referred to as non-Faradaic electrolysis (nFE). All previous work was done at room temperature and we have meanwhile found that temperature has a marked influence on the characteristics of nFE. Herein we present a preliminary report of the same.

Effect of Temperature

The main features of the effect of temperature on

non-Faradaic electrolysis are described below :

(1) Increase of temperature increases the extent of co-liberation i. e., the cathode gas contains a larger per cent of oxygen and the anode gas contains a larger per cent of hydrogen. In other words, there is more oxygen at the cathode and very much more hydrogen at the anode under otherwise similar conditions.

(2) But the most striking feature is the fact that co-liberation even at the anode (and the other non-Faradaic features more or less) persists up to a very high current density, and to some extent at a much higher concentration. For example, at room temperature the gases cease to be explosive at about 10mA/cm², whereas at 60° the gases are explosive (even) at 50mA/cm² or even higher in suitable systems. This is shown in Table 1.

idea of charged water molecules carrying the current. The observed effect of temperature naturally helps increased formation of (H₂O)⁺ and (H₂O)⁻ near the anode and cathode respectively. Secondly, increase of temperature increases their mobility to the corresponding opposite electrode and thus help co-liberation.

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TABLE 1

K ₂ SO ₄ 40°C				K ₂ SO ₄ 60°C				K ₂ SO ₄ 80°C			
Strength	% O ₂ at		% H ₂ at	Strength	% O ₂ at		% H ₂ at	Strength	% O ₂ at		% H ₂ at
	i/mA	Cathode	Anode		i/mA	Cathode	Anode		i/mA	Cathode	Anode
0.001(N)	22	10.4**	23.3**	0.001(N)	1	31.4**	56.0**	0.001(N)	25	16.7**	29.0**
	22	13.6**	23.6**		1	32.1**	57.8**		26	17.7**	26.6**
	25	13.5**	21.6**		5	30.6**	45.9**				
	25	14.4**	22.5**		10	26.8**	38.9**				
			25		17.4**	20.5**					
0.01(N)				0.01(N)	5	33.7**	45.6**	0.01(N)			
					5	32.0**	50.2**				
					10	24.8**	38.5**				
	36.5	5.0*	6.1*				35		15.2**	25.0**	
	36	6.0*	6.9*	40	11.4**	19.2**	39		14.8**	28.0**	
40	0.6	4.8*	45	10.4**	18.9**	40	15.6**	27.3**			
40	1.4	3.7*	60	13.4**	22.8**	41	16.0**	25.9**			
						60	12.3**	23.1**			
						60	12.3**	23.0**			
0.1(N)	39	1.2	0.6	0.1(N)	40	1.2	1.3	0.1(N)	40	16.9**	23.7**
	39	1.0	0		41	1.1	1.3		40	16.4**	23.5**
	40	0.6	0		45	0.2	0.8		60	12.1**	15.7**
	40	0.3	0		45	0.2	0.5		60	12.9**	17.2**
							80		9.0**	6.0*	
							80		9.8**	1.6	

N.B. : ** means strongly explosive ; * means mildly explosive ; others do not explode on sparking.

Thus the limitations of low current density and low concentration which we have so far found to be essential for production of non-Faradaic features are mostly removed by an increase of temperature. Keeping concentration low (~N/1000), it is possible to increase the current density to as high as 25mA/cm² or even higher and still get explosive gases at both the electrodes or at least at the cathode. This is illustrated in Table 1. Also the concentration zone over which co-liberation takes place gets very much extended at higher temperature so much so that N/100 or even N/10 concentrations can be used to yield explosive cathode and anode gases provided the temperature is suitably high. Thus the present work has very much extended the frontier of activity for study of non-Faradaic electrolysis.

Various theories have been suggested to explain the anomalous features of non-Faradaic electrolysis. We have critically examined all of them in a separate paper⁴ and favour the one involving the

Quantitation of Copper in Some of the Copper Base Alloys by Paper Chromatographic Technique

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In an earlier communication¹ a method of direct assessment suitable for determining uranyl ion by photodensitometer after its paper chromatographic separation was proposed. The procedure described for evaluating unknowns quantitatively from strips run simultaneously for knowns and unknowns proved better than other known methods of direct spot evaluation in paper chromatography. To apply this technique for metal ion estimations in alloys, attempts have been made in this communication to separate and estimate copper in some of the